

Heshang Gong 河上公 commentary on the Daodejing 道德经

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Entry tags: Sichuan Basin and Hanzhong Valley Region, Canonical texts, Early Chinese Traditions, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Religious Group, Early Chinese text, Text, Chinese Daoist Text, Cosmology, Daoist text, Daoism, Language, Afro-Asiatic, Chinese Religion, Cosmogony

The Heshang Gong 河上公 commentary, deemed to have been completed before the end of the Han 汉 dynasty, is the earliest complete commentary on the Daodejing 道德经 ("Classic of the Way and Virtue") that survived until the present day. It represents, together with Wang Bi's 王弼 edition, the most circulated edition of the Daodejing. The author, considered a Daoist hermit, is only known by the pseudonym Heshang Gong. His real name is unknown and very little is known about his life. The first mention of a Daodejing commentary bearing the name Heshang Gong appears in the catalogue of Daoist literature of the Sui shu 隋書: here an edition of the Daodejing in two parts, accompanied by a Heshang Gong's commentary (from the time of Han Wendi 文帝) is mentioned. Some biographical information is known from the preface to the commentary written by the Daoist Ge Xuan 葛玄 in the third century CE. Of him, it is said that he lived in a hut on the banks of the Huanghe 黄河 and that he devoted himself exclusively to the study of the Daodejing. There is also an anecdote that describes him as a sage with mystical abilities: after declining Wendi's invitation to court, when the emperor came to him seeking guidance on understanding the Daodejing, Heshang Gong is said to have ascended to heaven, floating in mid-air, admonishing the emperor - and then, according to this account, he finally provided the emperor with his commentary on the text. However, such an account is unrealistic for at least two reasons: firstly, the large number of synonymic compounds reveals a later date of the commentary's compilation; secondly, if the emperor had indeed received a copy, it would certainly have been catalogued in the Han shu 漢書. But thanks to direct references to the commentary or to Heshang Gong's proposed reading of the Daodejing in the Huainanzi and other texts, we know that it must have been compiled by the end of the later Han 后汉 (220 CE) at the latest - although the Laozi 老子 attached to it may have been interpolated by later editors. As pointed out by Robinet, the commentary uses a twofold register, serving both as a guide to individual self-cultivation practice (thus preparing the reader for the book's practical use as a guide to meditation) and as a political device for the state. In this way, the commentary reveals a Huanglao 黃老 approach, offering an understanding of the dao 道 on the one hand cosmological and on the other pragmatic and political. Methodologically, Heshang Gong uses an exegetical method distinctive of the Han period, namely the zhangju 章句, dividing the text into 81 chapters and glossing it sentence by sentence. The reading of the text proposed by Heshang Gong in his commentary introduces new concepts, absent or almost absent from the text, and gives particular prominence to certain ideas, such as that of unity or oneness (yi 一), which is recognized as an ordering principle. It makes extensive reference to concepts rooted in correlative cosmology, such as the principles of yin 陰 and yang 陽, theorizing a system of complete correspondence between cosmos, society and human beings, in which the sage embraces the one and emulates it through non-action, regulating his body as well as ordering the state. The philosophical analysis proposed in the commentary identifies the dao of heaven with the dao of the human being, theorizing a parallel development of the cosmic order, the socio-political order and individual longevity. From a prosodic point of view, compared to the bamboo and silk versions, the Daodejing accompanied by the Heshang Gong commentary amplifies the tendency to have four-character sentences. If some sentences of this type were already present in the manuscript editions, in the text of Heshang Gong, the 4-character sentences became a proper pattern. Both the received versions of Heshang Gong and Wang Bi manifest this tendency towards four-character sentences, basically achieved through the elimination of particles. Of the approximately 400

characters that have been eliminated in these editions, compared to the silk manuscripts, most are represented by particles such as zhi 之 or ye 也. For example, the following sentence from chapter 2: "有亡之相生也" in the Mawangdui editions became "故有無相生" in the Heshang Gong edition. In this sentence, another linguistic difference can be highlighted when compared to the earlier manuscript versions, namely the almost exclusive use of the negation wu 無 where the manuscripts have wang 亡. Furthermore, the Heshang Gong commentary provides titles for the individual chapters of the Daodejing, which almost serve as instructions for the reader, although these headings may have been added later by religious Daoists. For instance, the first chapter is titled Ti dao 體道 ("embodying the way"), the second, Yang shen 養身 ("nourishing the body/person"), the third, An min 安民 ("pacifying the people), and so on.

Date Range: 200 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Han empires

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

After the short-lived Qin dynasty (221–206 BCE), the Han empires (202 BCE–220 CE) were the second set of polities that ruled over the heartland of present-day China through a unified imperial system. The Liu clan who founded the Western Han (202 BCE–7 CE) emerged from the Chu region along the Yangzi River. Around the beginning of the 1st century CE, an affinal member of the imperial family seized power and founded the Xin Dynasty (9–23 CE). After a period of civil strife, a distant member of the Liu clan eventually founded the Eastern Han (25–220) that reunified the empire. The seat of the imperial house was moved from the western capital of Chang'an (modern-day Xi'an) to the eastern capital Luoyang.

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Xiong 熊, Tiejie 鐵基, and Chen 陳 Hongxing 紅星, eds. Laozi Jicheng 老子集成. Vol.1-15. Beijing: Zongjiao wenhua, 2011.
- Source 2: Heshang Gong 河上公, Wang Ka 王卡, Laozi Daodejing Heshang Gong zhangju 老子道德經河上公章句. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1993.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/wiki.pl?if=gb&chapter=29&remap=gb>
- Source 1 Description: 老子河上公章句

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/wiki.pl?if=gb&chapter=29&remap=gb>
- Source 1 Description: ctext 老子河上公章句
- Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/dao-de-jing>
- Source 2 Description: ctext 道德經

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

↳ Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

- Specify: The received editions of the Daodejing attached to the Heshang gong commentary are inked on paper. However, we do not have the original text, but later editions, probably interpolated by later scribes.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

- No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-ionic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: The Daodejing is considered part of the so-called "Daoist Canon" of reference for Religious Daoism (Daojiao 道教).

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is believed that the Daodejing, or at least part of the text, was conceived for being memorized and orally recited and transmitted, based on its rhymed structure. I. Robinet 1977 also pointed out that the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that the text could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

Notes: The authorship of the Daodejing is attributed to Laozi 老子 (Old Master), a semi-legendary figure whom classical historiography, beginning with Sima Qian's 司馬遷 *Shiji* 史記, dates back to the 6th century BCE. His biography is shrouded in legend: a contemporary of Confucius and a native of Chu 楚, Li 李 by surname, Er 耳 by given name, he allegedly served as archivist to the Zhou 周. As early as the early imperial period, with the mixing of native and Indian elements, a process of deification of the master began, which passed through the mythologizing of his biography: a legend was spawned concerning his miraculous birth, which occurred when he was already old and therefore wise, based on the very ambiguity of the name Laozi (old master/old child).

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: Also the life of Heshang Gong 河上公, the author of the commentary, is mysterious. His real name is unknown and he is only known as the hermit of the river bank. It is said that he used to live in a hut on the banks of the Huanghe 黃河 and that he devoted himself exclusively to the study of the Daodejing. He was believed to have mystical powers.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Notes: There are several editions of the Daodejing with sometimes significant variations in content, vocabulary, order of passages, and sections. The edition accompanied by the Heshang Gong commentary is one among many.

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– No

Notes: The Daodejing has been handed down through a philosophical-literary tradition. Various editions come with an appended commentary, as in the case of the Heshang Gong edition. In addition, several manuscript editions have been unearthed from ancient tombs. Since the Daodejing is also a benchmark for practitioners of the Daoist religious cult, these people also contributed to its transmission.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The Daodejing itself is not written in a sacred or religious language, but both the rhymed structure and the expressive complexity of the text, both linguistically and in terms of content, affect the book's mysticism. As for Heshang Gong's commentary, this greatly magnified the Daodejing's aura of mysticism through a reading of the text through the lenses of correlative cosmology and meditation.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Notes: I. Robinet 1977 pointed out that the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that the text could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas.

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Notes: I. Robinet 1977 pointed out that the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that the text could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: Starting at the beginning of the first millennium CE, the Daodejing has been taken as a reference text for the religious cults and ritual practices associated with Religious Daoism.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed

during rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the Daodejing edition accompanied by Heshang gong's commentary, there are several other editions of the text, either handed down from the philosophical-literary tradition (e.g. the edition commented by Wang Bi), or unearthed manuscript editions (as in the case of the two texts of Mawangdui, or the partial edition in three scrolls found in Guodian).

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The Daodejing did not originate as part of a collection of texts, but became part of the "Daoist Canon."

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Philosophical

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: None of the previous

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: The commentary does not outline a precise distinction between spirit and body, but it connects different kinds of spirits to bodily organs, and in particular, among these spirits, the hun 魂 and po 魄

are listed as related to the liver and the lungs.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 31 deals with war-avoidance and the ritual ceremonies for the deceased in the battlefield. The commentary specifies that in funeral rites the high officer stays on the right since they believed that the dead prefer yin. Also when the war is won, funeral rites need to be

observed to mourn the deceased.

- ↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?
 - No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high-god is present
 - No

Notes: The text does not explicitly mention a supreme high god.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions both shen 神 (as well as shenming 神明 and shenling 神靈) and gui 鬼.

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– Yes

Notes: The text refers to a sacrifice to the gods, the Tailao 太牢, in which cattle, pigs, and sheep are offered.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: The text does not provide precise information about these spirits. What is known is that they can either protect or harm humans.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization of pantheon?
– Specify: Not specified.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: None.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: Neither the Daodejing nor the Heshang Gong commentary guide divinatory practices, but some scholars, such as Sarah Allan, believe the text refers to the use of the shipan 式盤 (a divinatory instrument displaying a schematised version of the cosmos).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not advocate any particular virtues; on the contrary, the Daodejing strongly

distances itself from the so-called Confucian virtues (such as benevolence, dedication to study, righteousness, etc.), even more so in the transmitted editions (such as the Heshang Gong edition) if compared with the excavated versions of the text. Nonetheless, the term De 德, which can be translated as "virtue," is central to the text: it even gives the title to one of the two macro-sections of the book, the Dejing 德經.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The text does not address the readers through fictive kinship terminology, yet it employs the term mu 母 (mother) in reference to the Dao 道 itself. Examples can be found in various chapters, in lines such: 可以为天下母; 無名，天地之始。有名，萬物之母; 有国之母，可以长久。

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: Even if the book does not focus on the topic of welfare, both chapter 72 and chapter 75 are concerned with the welfare of the people, especially with the problem of the scarcity of livelihood.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education in China has been primarily restricted to males for centuries.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The Daodejing clearly condemns military action and war in various passages. The concept itself of wuwei 無為 (non-action or non-purposeful action) is consistently employed to justify the avoidance of war.

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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